

**FACTORS AFFECTING THE ACTIVITIES IN INDUSTRIAL
ENTERPRISES IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE
DEVELOPMENT AND THEIR EFFECTS ON THE REGIONAL
ECONOMY**

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ANNOTATION: In this article, the factors affecting the activity of industrial enterprises regional characteristics were analyzed.

KEY WORDS: industry, enterprise, innovation, added value, diversification, factor, financial and economic resources.

The development of any national economy depends on the balanced and sustainable development of its territories. In the sustainable development of regions and their territories, the importance of industrial sectors is high. Because industrial sectors, in addition to ensuring the rate of economic growth, create the basis for increasing the competitiveness of the economy by stimulating the diversification and localization of production. Processing of all raw materials mined in the industrial sector, created in production, diversification processes will be improved due to the production of various products from them. The practice of developed and high-growth countries in the world experience shows that their success was mainly due to structural changes in industrial sectors, in particular, in processing industries.

What sets the industry apart from other industries is the high level of inclusion in value creation. Added value is the sequence of the production process from the creation, processing, marketing and final consumption of a specific product.

Formation and development or level of innovative activity of enterprises change occurs as a result of the influence of certain factors. The enterprise is innovative During the objective and comprehensive research of the management of the activity, the problem of identifying and systematizing the factors affecting it will be urgent and insufficiently developed.

The basis of the methodology of effective management of many spheres of activity is the creation of a system that brings together modern knowledge and world

experience of performing this complex intellectual and highly responsible work. In this case, the development of the philosophy and concept of management of business industrial enterprises, its mission, strategy, goals, principles and other aspects typical of such systems should be of great importance. This is due to the fact that the industrial enterprise can achieve success only if these most important conceptual rules become the rules of all personnel behavior. According to the classics of scientific management, sound principles are more powerful in the hands of average people than the unsystematic and haphazard efforts of geniuses. This law of efficient operation is of particular importance in modern, extremely complex economic life. By the factor of innovative activity, we understand the conditions, reasons and indicators that affect the speed and description of the innovative growth of the enterprise. In this innovative process, as a result of the interaction of many factors, to the field comes out. The analysis of scientific literature shows that the impact on innovative activity the classification of transfer factors was not developed at the same time

Many authors have focused their attention on the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise. T.G. In her work, Filosofova noted the following factors that hinder innovation in industrial enterprises:

- lack of economic and financial resources, not enough from the state financing, high spending on innovation promotion, economic high level of risk, long period of innovation returns;
- production - lack of qualified personnel, new technologies, sales lack of necessary information about markets, innovation of the organization inability to quickly accept, lack of cooperation with other organizations, enterprises and scientific organizations;
- other factors - low price for innovative products by consumers demand, sufficient legal and regulatory bases in innovative activities, lack of regulation, insufficient innovation activity by the state lack of encouragement, poorly developed innovative infrastructure, lack of development in the technology market.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The Jizzakh branch of the Center for Economic Research and Reforms analyzed the work carried out in the industrial sector in the Jizzakh region during 2022 based on the information of the State Statistics Committee.

In January-December 2022, a total of 11,149.5 billion soums worth of industrial

(Source: Prepared based on the data of the Jizzakh Region Statistics Committee)

The highest growth rates were recorded in Gallaorol (137.6%), Forish (113.7%) and Pakhtakor (107.8%) districts, Arnasoy (87.8%) Yangiabad (98.1%) and Zarbdor (98.2%) districts, the volume of production was less compared to the corresponding period of 2021.

63 percent of the total volume of manufactured industrial products is contributed by Jizzakh city (34%), Gallaorol (19%) and Zafarabad (10%) districts. Although the share of industry in the GNP increased to 13.1% and increased by 0.9 points compared to 2021, it is 2 times less than the national average (26.7%). (13th place)

The volume of industrial products produced per capita was 7,639.4 thousand soums (10th place), the growth rate was 105.4% (7th place).

Jizzakh city (20,210,000 soums), Zafarabad (21,237,000 soums), Dostlik (12,668,000 soums), Gallaorol (11,740,000 soums) and Pakhtakor (8,427,000 soums) industrial products produced per capita in the districts are higher

than the average level of the region, the lowest indicators were recorded in Bakhmal (616 thousand soums) and Yangiabad (1 464 thousand soums) districts.

Processing industry accounts for 94% of total industrial products.

The share of the mining industry - 2%, the share of electricity supply, gas, steam supply and artificial climate production - 3%, the share of water supply, sewage, waste collection and disposal - It was 1%.

Manufacture of textile products (31%), manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers (19%), manufacture of other non-ferrous mineral products (16%) and manufacture of food products (13%) within the processing industry directions have the highest share.

696 new enterprises were established in the field of industry, the total number of industrial enterprises was 4,469, the share of KBS in the sector was 49.9%.

118 companies with foreign capital participate in the industry, making up 52% of the total number of enterprises with foreign capital participation.

According to preliminary data, in January 2023, regional enterprises will spend 760.8 billion. Soums worth of industrial products were produced, and compared to January 2022, the physical volume index* of industrial production was 90.7%. According to the contribution of the industry producing the largest share in the structure of industrial production, its share in the total industrial production was 95.7%.

As of September 1, 2023, 2,679 industrial enterprises are operating in Jizzakh region, of which 732 (27.3% of the total number of operating enterprises) are located in Jizzakh city, and 364 (13.6%) are located in Sharaf Rashidov district. , 309 of them (11.5%) correspond to Ghallaorol district, 248 (9.3%) to Zomin district and 171 (6.4%) to Zarbdar district.

In our opinion, the results of the research are the innovative activity of the enterprise enabling and consequential to determine and implement the level improving the methods of evaluating the innovative activity of industrial enterprises creates conditions for the development of complex indicators. Also each additional by developing industrial enterprises in the region on an innovative basis value creation serves as a locomotive for the development of the regional economy does.

In their Address to the Assembly, they noted the following: "In 12 leading branches of industry, programs of modernization and strengthening of competitiveness are being implemented rapidly. As a result, economic growth last year was 5.6 percent. The volume of production of industrial products increased by 6.6%, export - by 28%.

Our gold-currency reserves increased by 2.2 billion dollars during 2019 and reached 28.6 billion dollars. Ensuring macroeconomic stability and curbing inflation in 2020 is our main task in the process of economic reforms. Digital technologies not only increase the quality of products and services, but also reduce excess costs. The regulation of the price of 37 types of products and services by the state has a negative impact on free competition. Taking this into account, we should now focus not on setting prices, but on reducing prices and increasing quality by ensuring healthy competition between enterprises. Studying the international experience, it is necessary to open the way for the private sector to the monopolistic areas where competition can be introduced and thereby create a competitive environment.

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which has a negative impact on the level of innovative activity is presented above it requires a lot of money to solve the problems.

Social factors include the demographic situation, the level of social tension, and the number of workers living conditions, wellness at the enterprise, sports and cultural activities organization, general cultural and educational level of personnel, etc can be entered. These are effective and full of production resources of the enterprise serves to ensure corporate development and formation of human capital.

Analysis of organizational and management factors in the development of innovative infrastructure level, effective innovation management, in the implementation of innovations organization of marketing strategy, innovation financing, helps to determine the suitability of the organizational structure to the tasks of innovative activity.

In our opinion, the factors affecting innovative activity it is necessary to classify according to the level of management.

Factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise according to the level of management in the classification, the factors that directly or indirectly affect the enterprise, as well as the level of its innovative activity and the enterprise it can be noted that it changes the factors that cannot be obtained.

Based on the above, innovative activity according to the level of management classification of factors is the most important in considering issues of expanding and evaluating the level of innovative activity of the enterprise.

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